

Minutes EB23-05
Meeting of the SeqCode Executive Board
6 December 2023 @ 7h00 (EST)

Attendance

Maria Chuvochina (MC)	- Chair Reconciliation Commission
Phil Hugenholtz (PH)	- Member without portfolio
Kostas Konstantinidis (KK)	- Chair, Standards Working Group
Anna-Louise Reysenbach (ALR)	- Vice Chair
Luis Miguel Rodriguez (LMR)	- Chair, Registry Working Group
Iain Sutcliffe (IS)	- Chair, Legislative Commission
Fanus Venter (FV)	- Secretary
Barny Whitman (BW)	- Chair
Fengping Wang (FW)	- Member without portfolio

1. Welcome

BW welcomed the members of the Executive Board.

2. Additions to the Agenda

Response time of the Registry (to be discussed as under the item Registry and Nomenclature Working Group)

3. Matters Arising/Action points from the previous meeting

Action items from previous meeting

1. MC to prepare a letter to the Editors of relevant journals on how they can obtain relevant information related to the registration of names prior to publication.

MC has contacted the editors of various journals but she had no further response from them.

2. KK to follow-up on the NSF's RCN and ICB funding

Proposal to be submitted by the end of 2023

3. FW to look for Chinese funding opportunities.

FW indicated that it is important to note that Chinese funding has to be used in China. Options to be explored will be workshops focusing on how to make use of the SeqCode or the development of basic coding skills which could also be used to develop the Registry. FW and LMR will also explore the possibility of a joint PhD student or Post-doc who would address some of the development needs of the Registry as part of a wider project addressing specific scientific questions.

Future action items

1. EB to prepare a formal report on the activities of the SeqCode for submission to ISME communications after January 2024.

4. Reports from Commissions and Working Groups

Legislative Commission

The public discussion of the Whitman et al. proposal is still ongoing until 10 January. FV will remind members via email of the opportunity to participate in the discussion.

Standards Working Group

No new issues to report

Registry and Nomenclature Working Group

There are currently 29 lists to be finalized. LMR indicated that there has been an increased activity on the Registry and that the median response time is 3 to 4 weeks at present. KK indicated that this is of concern to some of the end-users and ways to improve the situation were discussed.

After some initial training Melandre van Lill joined the curation team to assist with checking the genome quality requirements. PH was tasked to investigate the possibility of continued funding from ISME to support her involvement after February

Assistance is required for the checking of the proposed names. A call will be made to the SeqCode community to look for additional volunteers. LMR and MC will look at the possible incorporation of GAN in the registry and if an option to provide seed words (stems) could be added.

Reconciliation Commission

The discussion of the proposal for validation of a name linked to a poor-quality genome to ensure the stability of the names of the higher-ranking taxa has been completed and will be discussed by the Commission on 7 December.

5. Coordinating SeqCode amendments to remain consistent with the ICNP

The incorporation of ranks of Kingdom and Domain in the SeqCode in line with the decisions of the ICSP was discussed. Although there was no objection to these ranks, it was decided that changes to the SeqCode to incorporate these will not be an immediate priority. Based on Rule 23e of the SeqCode, legitimate names validly published under the ICNP remain legitimate under the SeqCode. This will likely provide the necessary protection for these names.

6. Application for ISME19 workshop and roundtable

FV reported that the proposal for the workshop was not supported. The call for round table discussions is open and MC will prepare and circulate a proposal.

7. Redacted

8. Conference and Meeting Updates

A number of EB members attended and presented at the BISMIS meeting in Guangzhou, China in November. They also participated in a round table discussion on the use of the SeqCode and the future of both codes.

BW also attended the WDCM meeting in China where interest in the SeqCode was shown by several of the delegates.

EB members are encouraged to list SeqCode presentations and share material linked to these presentations on the shared drive.

9. Interactions with the ICSP

The discussions at BISMIS again emphasised the need to operate the SeqCode and ICNP in harmony. Any efforts to merge them in the near future may however be premature. Prof On, the ICSP Secretary for Subcommittees recently indicated that changes to the ICNP to better accommodate uncultivated bacteria may soon be proposed. Final decisions on the way forward will therefore be postponed until we have greater clarity.

As members of the SeqCode EB, we should continue to encourage the submission of type material to culture collections whenever possible.

10. Interactions with other initiatives to have sequenced based Nomenclature Codes

There are currently no concrete suggestion or initiative to discuss

The meeting was adjourned.

New action items

1. FV to circulate the minutes of this meeting to the EB for their comments and approval.
2. FV to remind the SeqCode Community via email of the discussion of the proposal to amend the SeqCode, and the SeqCode prize. The help of volunteer nomenclature curators will also be requested.
3. PH to investigate the possibility of continued funding from ISME for work on the registry.
4. LMR and MC to look into the possible incorporation of GAN in the registry.
5. MC to prepare a proposal for a round table discussion at ISME19.
6. Redacted

Ongoing or future action items

1. EB to prepare a formal report on the activities of the SeqCode for submission to ISME communications after January 2024.
2. KK to investigate possible RCN funding

Minutes prepared by FV, December 7, 2023

Approved December 11, 2023